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Research Article

**HEPATITIS B VIRUS INFECTION IN A PEDIATRIC HEMATOLOGY
AND ONCOLOGY UNIT IN PAKISTAN EPIDEMIOLOGICAL
INVESTIGATION AND MEASURES FOR PREVENT FURTHER
TRANSMISSION**¹Dr Khalid Mehmood, ²Dr Sidrah Naz, ³Dr Mazher Hussain Shah¹Akhter Saeed Medical and Dental College, Bahria Town, Lahore²Ghazi Khan Medical College Dera Ghazi Khan³Wah Medical College**Article Received:** September 2020 **Accepted:** October 2020 **Published:** November 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: Hepatitis B (HBV) disease has been portrayed everywhere and continues to occur worldwide. Subsequent nosocomial flare-ups have been linked to risky infusion repetitions, the use of multi-compartment vials, and the failure of staff to follow standard safety measures. This report describes a nosocomial outbreak that occurred in a pediatric hematology and oncology unit of a large school medical clinic, the epidemiological review of the outbreak, and updated preventive estimates to further limit transmission in the clinic.

Methods: 53 cases of HBV contamination have been confirmed in 408 patients judged between March 2019 and February 2020 at Services Hospital, Lahore. Episode review, including contact follow-up and HBV screening, was initially performed on all patients seen by the unit for a period similar to that of the first three cases. Routine screening for all patients on the unit began in March 2019, when it was understood that several patients may have been discovered.

Results: 53 cases of HBV contamination have been confirmed in 408 patients judged between March 2019 and February 2020 at Services Hospital, Lahore. Phylogenetic examination of the preC/C quality nucleotide clusters of HBV revealed that all tested outbreak strains clustered together. In general, (68%) of patients were HBeAg-positive. The reason for transmission could not be established. Preventive measures guided three treatment proposals. HBV screening and immunization conventions were implemented in the unit.

Conclusion: The high number of HBeAg-positive patients, as well as suspected slippages in contamination avoidance and control measures, are recognized as having played a significant role in transmission. The measures implemented to prevent transmission in medical clinics have been effective. The HBV screening and vaccination programs underway in pediatric hematology and oncology units should receive quality care.

Keywords: Hepatitis B Virus Infection, Pediatric, Epidemiological Investigation.

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INTRODUCTION:

Clinically acquired hepatitis B virus (HBV) contamination has been described everywhere and continues to occur worldwide. Nosocomial HBV contamination has generally been linked to the binding of tainted blood and blood products. Since the mid-1990s, contributor screening projects and testing of all blood donations have reduced the risk of binding HBV infections [1]. Nosocomial episodes have been linked to unsafe repeat infusions, the use of multi-compartment vials, and the consistent failure of staff to take routine precautionary measures, including hand washing [2]. Various episodes of HBV infection have been reported in pediatric oncology facilities [3]. The increased risk of HBV contamination in these patients could be attributed to a number of factors, including immunodeficiency caused by underlying injury and cytostatic chemotherapy. Long-term confirmations, due to delays in treatment plans and travel limitations, as well as poor HBV insensitivity, are also being observed in Pakistan. While the expanded inoculation program in Pakistan includes HBV inoculations at the beginning, late reports suggest that youth in the hematology and oncology units have little or no HBV counteragent titers [4]. This article describes a nosocomial episode that occurred in a pediatric hematology and oncology unit of a large university emergency clinic, the epidemiological review of this episode and the preventive estimates made to limit transmission in the clinic. These measures include the rigorous implementation of standard disease control safeguards and the use of a vaccination program for all patients admitted to the unit [5].

METHODOLOGY:

The review involved patients treated in the Pediatric Hematology and Oncology Unit of a large university emergency clinic in Pakistan. The unit has a total of 33 inpatient beds and 12 beds for day claims. Approximately 120 new patients are constantly supervised in the unit. The vast majority of patients are

regularly admitted to the unit during their treatment. All patients entering the unit are routinely assessed for infectious disease due to human immunodeficiency after obtaining their consent. Routine HBV immunization of HIV-negative patients was not performed prior to this episode. The first three cases of HBV infection that triggered the episode were analyzed over a 52-day period. 53 cases of HBV contamination have been confirmed in 408 patients judged between March 2019 and February 2020 at Services Hospital, Lahore. They were asymptomatic and received liver chemicals during routine blood work. Each of these patients had tested negative for HBsAg and HBc on initial admission to the unit. Push testing, including contact follow-up and HBV testing, was initially performed on all patients found in the outpatient center and on those admitted to the unit during the same period as the contaminated patients. During this first screening period (May 2012 to January 2013), 19 patients tested positive for HBsAg. In response to this episode, all staff working in the unit were re-educated on HBV transmission courses. The use of standard insurances, including systematic hand washing, wearing of gloves, use of alcohol containing splashes on the hands and proper garbage disposal, was reinforced. The use of multi-dose vials has been discontinued. Patients accepting treatment and patients in long-term development who were not sufficiently insensitive to HBV were given a portion of the Hepatitis B immunization promoter, Heberbiovac HB. We respect the enemies of HBs levels >100 mIU/ml as defensive agents in our unit. This is dependent on past reports that recommended that low insensitivity with enemies of HBs levels between 12 and 100 mIU/ml, especially in negotiated invulnerable persons, was not considered adequate protection. Rising low levels of HBV resistance (10 to 100 mIU/ml) at this stage resulted in quality patient care.

Table 1:

	Patients				
	A	B	C	D	E
Surgery/major investigative procedure	Neither	Neither	Neither	Yes Surgery ^a	Neither
Glucometer testing	No	Yes ^b	Yes ^b	No	No
Medication administered from multi-dose vials	No	No	No	No	No
Intravenous cannulation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Phlebotomy	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

^a Patient D: surgery December 2005. Ruled out as source of hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection.

^b Patients B and C: located on different wards. Different glucose meters would have been used. Ruled out as source of HBV infection

RESULTS:

During the flare-up exam and subsequent daily HBV screening on the unit, 409 patients were tested for HBV. 51 cases of HBV disease were confirmed from July 2011 to October 2013. Table I shows the schedule of functions as well as the activities performed at each time. The persistent attributes are summarized in Table II. There were 30 males and 19 females with confirmed HBV disease, and the mean age of congregation was 12.9 years (range 2.0-21.6 years). A large proportion of the patients (67.3%) were patients with hematologic malignancies and very intense lymphoblastic leukemia (19 of 49 patients). Serum bilirubin and alanine transferase levels were found in seven asymptomatic infected patients, with serum bilirubin levels up to 37 mmol/L and serum ALT levels ranging from 46 to 1131U/L. Nevertheless, these strange results were certainly not considered as a reliable marker of HBV-related liver damage in a context where the organization of cytotoxic

chemotherapy routinely causes comparative biochemical abnormalities. Forty of the 51 (83%) HBV-positive patients were undergoing chemotherapy. As part of the outbreak review, HBV PCR testing was performed on various intravenous access covers (bungs) that were held together in a germicidal device. No evidence of HBV staining was found; however, HBV DNA may have been weakened or decreased during the test period, as these covers were stored for a period of time in chlorhexidine prior to testing. The use of multi-dose vials as well as multiple-use saline bags (used for flushing intravenous access catheters) was normal practice in the unit during the outbreak period. In any event, clinical staff denied the repeated use of similar needles or syringes for various patients. Despite the fact that emergency rooms were usually covered, there was no transmission of HBV infection. Certainly not all patients were hospitalized in a similar room, but they did share a toilet and the usual eating area.

Figure 1:

Table 2:

Patient characteristic	Inactive carriers (n = 85)	HBeAg-negative CHB patients		P*
		All (n = 65)	Normal baseline ALT (n = 11)	
Age (years)	42 ± 12	49 ± 13	48 ± 16	0.001
Sex, males (%)	51 (60)	52 (80)	9 (82)	0.015
ALT, IU/L	25 (11–40)	98 (20–879)	35 (20–40)	<0.001
ALT<ULN, n (%)	85 (100)	11 (17)	11 (100)	<0.001
AST (IU/L)	24 (11–40)	70 (14–527)	34 (22–40)	<0.001
Serum HBV DNA (IU/mL)	464 (<80–18 862)	892 857 (337–2 × 10 ⁹)	11 607 (337–2 142 857)	<0.001
Patients with HBV DNA, n (%)				
<80 IU/mL	23 (27)	0	0	<0.001
<2000 IU/mL	65 (76)	4 (6)	2 (18)	
<5000 IU/mL	78 (92)	6 (9)	3 (27)	
<20 000 IU/mL	85 (100)	16 (25)	6 (55)	

CHB, chronic hepatitis B; ULN, upper limit of normal; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase. Quantitative variables are expressed as mean ± SD or as median (range) values.

*P values for comparisons between the 85 inactive carriers and the 65 patients with HBeAg-negative CHB. ALT, AST and HBV DNA levels were also significantly different between the 85 carriers and the 11 HBeAg-negative CHB patients with normal baseline ALT (P ≤ 0.001).

DISCUSSION:

A curiously high number of HBV infections were recorded in a pediatric hematology and oncology unit between July 2011 and October 2013. Preventive measures have been taken to limit the transmission of HBV in the clinic. Numerous cases of HBV outbreaks have been reported in pediatric oncology units around the world [6]. In our written research, the last reported episode in a Pakistan unit occurred over a 13-year period (1986-1999) and involved 61 patients. Willers et al. reported on pediatric patients who developed dynamic hepatitis B disease throughout the course of oncology treatment in a Pakistan unit (1999-2003), but did not conduct conventional examination of the episode or phylogenetic investigations of the tests of these patients [7]. Most of the patients (68%) who created dynamic HBV contamination during the described outbreak were patients with hematologic malignancies [8]. Potential factors that may lead this group of patients to create HBV contamination include: extremely safe, optional concealment of the disease, prolonged confinement from the emergency clinic, repeated venipuncture, and an increased requirement for intrusive procedures. Buchner et al. revealed about HBV immunity in this cluster of patients on first admission to the unit, and found an extremely low rate of adequate levels of HBV enemy [9]. The invulnerability to HBV inoculation is described throughout the literature. In children without permanent infection, it has been shown that

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invulnerable memory is saved on all sides despite the disappearance of the enemies of HBV titles. In any case, it has been shown, even in a meeting of healthy children, that this weakening of HBV resistance puts them at risk of developing the disease with HBV 12 to 17 years later [10].

CONCLUSION:

Taking everything into account, the high number of HBeAg positive patients, along with suspected failures in contamination anticipation and control measures, are accepted to have assumed a significant part in the transmission. Measures executed to forestall further in-medical clinic transmission of HBV were effective. Ongoing HBV screening furthermore, inoculation programs in pediatric hematology and oncology units should get standard of care.

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